

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

RISIS Datasets – Academic Patents in Europe

Peter Neuhäusler and Rainer Frietsch

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1 Introduction

The deepening of the RISIS Patent Database aims at improving the identification of the patent output of universities (academic patents). Academic patents cover two instances, either a university is listed among the applicants, or an inventor can be identified as being a researcher from a university (academic inventor). Most studies on patents by universities only cover the first of these instances when the patents are filed (owned) by the universities. There are different strategic or procedural reasons that universities are not applicant (owner) of all the inventions that originate from universities.

For example, the applicant of a patent might be a company when the university found a commercialization partner for the invention in an early phase before the publication of the patent. Another example is the case that the invention was made in a contract research project where the contractor is a company that claims the ownership. The most frequent cases are the application by the inventor(s), in this case by the professors or researchers that were participating in the project. In the first decade of this century, many countries changed or adapted their regulations concerning the ownership of patents by universities (Geuna and Rossi 2011).

The main aim was to improve the commercialization of university-invented technologies, on the one hand to increase the use of publicly funded knowledge, but on the other hand, the motivation was also to generate additional income for the universities, thereby lifting the burden of public budget allocations. The role model for these revisions and adaptations was the so called Bayh-Dole-Act of the USA that was released already in 1980. Germany, for example, abolished its previously existing so called 'professors privilege' in 2002 that - up till then - allowed the professors to file the inventions by themselves, while from 2002 onwards the ownership and therefore the right to file a patent is with the university. Several other countries, for example France, Sweden or Italy (see Lissoni et al. 2009), have also implemented Bayh-Dole-Act-like regulation in the early 2000s.

In companion with the new regulation, many countries also installed technology transfer organizations (TTOs) that were meant to manage the filing and the commercialization processes. While in most cases this was not an economically successful endeavour, the numbers of university-filed (owned) patents increased in most countries. However, even after the change of the regulations still a considerable number of patents - in case of Germany it is about 50% (see Dornbusch/Neuhäusler et al. 2015) - of the inventions made by staff members (academic inventors) of universities are not filed by the universities, but by companies, individuals or other research organisations. This leads to the fact that there are essentially three groups of "patents by universities" that can be analysed independently, namely a) patents filed by universities (university is listed as an applicant) b) patents invented by universities (university is not listed as an applicant but university personnel is named as an inventor) and c) both taken together forming the group of academic patents.

The challenge, however, is to identify university-invented patents. In order to do this, a matching of author names from Elsevier Scopus with inventor names from PATSTAT was performed for the EU-27 countries as well as Great Britain (for more details regarding the methodology see Dornbusch et al. (2013)). The underlying assumption here is that authors of scientific papers in fact are university (or PRO) researchers. Yet, this name matching has the challenge of identifying homonyms for very common names, e.g. Thomas Müller in Germany, which can immensely bias the results. In order to counteract this effect, there is a system of checks that goes beyond the name of the person, i.e. we

check whether the patent and the publication are within a similar time window, we check whether the author and inventor live in the same region (NUTS-2)¹ and we check whether the patent and the publication are within a similar technological area via a rough concordance of technology fields in patents and scientific fields in publications. These selection criteria are also displayed in Figure 1. Only if all criteria were met, an author/inventor pair was accepted as a "match" and therefore the person was labelled as an academic inventor with all of her/his patents coded as university-invented patents.

Figure 1 Overview of the selection criteria for the matching of author- and inventor names

2) Organization		3) Names		4) Time		5) Location		6) Subject	
X uni-inv = 1		if (a names match + b time match + c location match + d subject match)							
	↓		↑		↑		↑		↑
	Organization matching	Name matching	Time window matching	Location matching	Classification matching				
PATSTAT	?	Full strings of last- and first name	Priority year	NUTS3-Codes and distance matrix	IPC classification = WIPO 34				
SCOPUS	Author affiliation = university	Full strings of last- and first name	Publication year: One year time-lag and time-window	NUTS3-Codes and distance matrix	Scopus classification: fine- / coarse-grained				

Source: Adapted from Dornbusch et al. (2013).

After the matching and thus the identification of academic patents has been performed, we are able to analyse academic patents in Europe more deeply.

2 Results at the country level

In Figure 2, the country-wise transnational patents filed by universities (upper panel of Figure 2) are plotted and compared against academic patents (lower panel of Figure 2). Germany, France and Great Britain show the largest numbers of university filed patents with an increasing trend over the years. In contrast to the transnational patents filed by universities, i.e. patents where the university is stated as the patent applicant, the lower panel of Figure 2 provides information about the academic patents by country, i.e. patents filed by universities plus patents invented by personnel located at the universities in the given countries. Similarly, we can observe the largest number of academic patents from Germany and France, but in total the number of patents is at a higher level as the "hidden share" of university-invented patents is included in the statistics on academic patents.

¹ For the regionalization of European regions "Pelias" (<http://pelias.io>) was used, which allows a geocoding of addresses in terms of longitude and latitude. Pelias essentially is a search engine for locations worldwide, powered by open data. It turns addresses and place names into geographic coordinates, and vice versa (<https://github.com/pelias/pelias>).

Figure 2 Patents filed by universities and academic patents

The difference between looking at university-filed vs. academic patents becomes even more evident in Figure 3, where both numbers are annually plotted by country. In France and Germany, the university-filed patents have increased over the years, which makes the gap between university-filed and academic patents smaller. In Spain, the gap is rather small throughout the whole time period, whereas it is rather large in Italy.

Finally, Figure 4 shows the shift in ownership structure of academic patents in Germany over time, which can basically be calculated for every country in Europe. We can see that there is a major shift away from single inventor ownership to university ownership. In addition, the share of company owned academic patents decreases over time. This surely is an effect of the abolishment of the "professor's privilege" in Germany. Whether this has led to an increase in academic patents overall, however, is subject to further research.

Figure 4 University-filed vs. academic patents by country

Figure 5 Ownership of academic patents, the example of Germany

3 Results at the level of single universities

A final challenge that we had to face regarding the academic patents is their identification at the micro-level, i.e. the level of universities. Until recently, only aggregate level analyses, i.e. country-, technology field level etc. were possible because university names within PATSTAT and SCOPUS are not standardized, implying that universities cannot uniquely be identified in the data. The solution for this problem is a matching of university applicants from PATSTAT with the ETER database. The European Tertiary Education Register (ETER), which has also been developed within RISIS, is a European-level database providing a reference list of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Europe and data at the institutional level on HEIs' activities and outputs (<https://eter-project.com/>). The advantage of the ETER database for academic patents is that it contains unified university names, which can be matched to the university names in PATSTAT, so the academic inventors can be assigned to a unified university name. On this basis, university-level analyses of academic patents become possible. The matching is based on harmonized and non-harmonized applicant names in PATSTAT and the university names from ETER.

For the matching, several steps were performed:

1. Data cleaning: removal of legal forms, umlauts, special characters, etc. from university names
2. Match exact name of the university + country
3. Match name of the university with "like" + country
4. Match exact English name + country
5. Match name English name with "like" + country
6. Match university acronym + country
7. Match city (e.g. Berlin) + general keyword search ("univ", "tech", etc.) + country
8. Repeat steps 2-7 without country comparison
9. Manual match of largest universities
10. In PATSTAT: Repeat for the harmonized hrm-l2 name from KU Leuven, doc_std_name and person_name, in Scopus: only organization name

Table 1: Exemplary overview of the matching and name harmonization process

Name PATSTAT	Country PATSTAT	Name ETER	Name ETER English	Acronym	City	Country ETER	Matched	# pat.
ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH	Ecole Polytechnique Federal de Lausanne	Federal Institute of Technology Lausanne	EPFL	Fribourg	CH	1	80
Universite Catholique De Louvain	BE	Universite catholique de Louvain	UCLouvain	UCL	Brussels	BE	1	166
Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	DK	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	Technical University of Denmark	DTU	Naestved	DK	1	1154
The Royal College of Art	GB	Royal College of Art	Royal College of Art	RCA	London	UK	1	12

In sum, this led to a matching rate of 86% of all PATSTAT applicant names being assigned to a unified university name from the ETER database (25,824 out of 30,191). In terms of patents covered, this share even increases to 96%, i.e. nearly all academic patents have been assigned to a unified university name (213,674 out of 222,822). Currently, final tests and validations of the matching and name harmonization are being performed. Once this is finished, the academic patents can be analysed at the level of individual universities for the countries within Europe.

Exemplary analyses in Figure 6 show that with the help of the matching of Scopus and PATSTAT to ETER academic patents can be analyzed at the level of single countries. Here, the patent intensity for some of the top patenting universities are compared to the citation rates of the patent portfolios of the respective universities.

Figure 6 Ownership of academic patents, the example of Germany

Note: Bubble size: Nr. of academic patents; Only universities with >100 academic patents between 2000-2020 that have employee information in ETER are shown.

4 References

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